

Agrarian structure in Poland and Ukraine (history, present state and future)¹

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Abstract

La structure agraire actuelle de la Pologne et de l'Ukraine est très différente. La première est dominée par des exploitations agricoles gérées par des particuliers, ayant généralement le statut d'exploitation familiale. Il existe peu de sociétés holding agricoles et environ 600 coopératives agricoles. Les exploitations familiales constituent la base du système agricole et le législateur a soutenu et continuera de soutenir ces entités à l'avenir. L'exploitation moyenne en Pologne est d'environ 12 ha. En Ukraine, par contre, plus de 60 % des terres agricoles d'une superficie comprise entre 200 et 2 000 ha sont louées. Les exploitations agricoles revêtent une grande importance. Compte tenu de son statut de candidat à l'adhésion à l'Union européenne, l'Ukraine devrait procéder à une réforme pour renforcer la position des agriculteurs ukrainiens.

Die derzeitige Agrarstruktur Polens und der Ukraine ist recht unterschiedlich. In Polen dominieren landwirtschaftliche Betriebe, die von Einzelpersonen geführt werden und im Allgemeinen den Status eines Familienbetriebs haben. Es gibt nur wenige landwirtschaftliche Holdinggesellschaften und etwa 600 landwirtschaftliche Genossenschaften. Die landwirtschaftlichen Familienbetriebe sind die Grundlage des landwirtschaftlichen Systems, und der Gesetzgeber hat solche Einheiten unterstützt und wird sie auch in Zukunft unterstützen. Der durchschnittliche landwirtschaftliche Betrieb in Polen ist etwa 12 ha groß. In der Ukraine hingegen sind mehr als 60 % der landwirtschaftlichen Flächen mit einer Größe zwischen 200 und 2.000 ha gepachtet. Der landwirtschaftliche Besitz ist von großer Bedeutung. Im Hinblick auf ihren Status als Beitrittskandidat zur Europäischen Union sollte die Ukraine eine Reform durchführen, um die Position der ukrainischen Landwirte zu stärken.

1. Introduction

Poland and Ukraine are neighbouring countries, and agriculture plays a critical role in both. Ukraine has been a sovereign state since 1991. However, since 2014 it is a country that has been associated with the European Union. The beginnings of the history of Poland as a separate country date back to the mid-ten century. In 1922 the main part of the modern Ukraine became one of the Republics of the Soviet Union. Poland, on the other hand, became after Second World War a socialist country in the

¹ The article was prepared as part of the AMU university grant addressed to scientists from Ukraine. Some of the issues contained in the article were presented during the Swiss-Polish Seminar, which took place at the University of Lucerne on July 26, 2022, "Selected legal and economic issues related to running agricultural activities in Poland and Ukraine" prepared by Faculty of Law of the University of Luzern, Switzerland, and the Faculty of Law and Administration of the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań, Poland.

Eastern Bloc. The systemic transformation in 1989 that brought Poland into the market economy was of key importance, and in 2004 membership in the European Union. Due to the neighbourhood as well as historical conditions, the relations between the indicated countries and citizens are very good. Poland supports Ukraine's efforts to join the European Union.

The aim of this article is to indicate the development of legal regulations concerning the agrarian structure in Poland and Ukraine. Due to the limited scope of the article, only selected issues related to the history and the current state will be presented. The likely directions of future changes will also be indicated.

2. Legal regulations concerning the agrarian structure in Poland

In the interwar period (1918-1939), agricultural land in Poland was under special protection, which resulted from Art. 99 of the March Constitution (Act of March 17, 1921)². According to this provision, "land, as one of the most important factors in the existence of the Nation and the State, cannot be traded unlimitedly. (...) The agricultural system of the Republic of Poland is to be based on farms capable of proper production and being personal property³." In the interwar period, leasing of agricultural land was also popular.

It is worth adding that over the centuries, from the 11th century onwards, part of today's Ukraine area was part of Poland, and then the Polish–Lithuanian Commonwealth, as well as the 1st and then 2nd Republics of Poland (1918-1939). Therefore, the regulations presented below were in force in Poland and in some areas of today's Ukraine.

In the interwar period, agricultural reform laws were introduced that had an impact on the expansion and creation of farms. In accordance with the Act of July 15, 1920 on the implementation of the land reform⁴, the principles of its implementation concerned, inter alia, the compulsory purchase of large-owned land, with an area below a certain statutory maximum, e.g. land surplus: over 60 hectares of total area in estates located in industrial and suburban districts and over 400 hectares of total area in estates located in some parts of the lands of the former Prussian partition and the eastern territories of the Republic of Poland⁵, a surplus of over 180 hectares of total area in properties located in the remaining parts of the Republic of Poland. Obviously, the owner of the property or properties subject to compulsory purchase was entitled to remuneration. The next Act of December 28, 1925 on the implementation of the agricultural reform⁶ indicated in Article 1 that the agricultural system of the Republic of Poland would be based on farms of various types and sizes, which would be strong, healthy and capable of high levels of production, and which would be the private property of their owners.

² Constitution of the Republic of Poland, March 17, 1921; <http://libr.sejm.gov.pl/tek01/txt/kpol/e1921.html>[Accessed on: 09.09.2022].

³ P. Kociubiński, *Powojenne przekształcenia własnościowe w świetle konstytucji*, Warszawa 2013.

⁴ Journal of Laws of 1920 r. no 70, item 462 as amended.

⁵ See more M. Stanulewicz, *Reforma rolna jako próba regulacji stosunków agrarnych w Polsce. Koncepcje i próby ich realizacji latach 1918 – 1944*, [in:] *Reformy rolne w Polsce międzywojennej i powojennej*, ed. E. Borkowska-Bagieńska, W. Szafranski, Poznań 2008, pp 11 and next.

⁶ Journal of Laws of 1926, no 1, item. 1 as amended.

The introduction of the new system included, inter alia, creating independent farms, expanding existing dwarf farms to the size of independent economic units, creating small farms for horticultural and vegetable production, creating gardens for workers and officials, etc. near cities and industrial centers.

Before World War II, the Polish countryside was diverse in terms of social and economic development. In 1931, the land covered an area of 37.9 million hectares. Farms with an area of less than 50 ha totaled 21.8 million ha (57.6 %), while those with an area of at least 50 ha, i.e. landed property, totaled 9.8 million ha (25.8 %). Small and medium-sized units (up to 10 ha) prevailed in number, together constituting 89 %. Landowners accounted for only 0.5 % of all farms, covering 25.8 % of the total land⁷. In the period from 1921 to 1939, certain changes took place in the agrarian structure, consisting in a decrease in the amount of land owned by landowners and public ownership in favor of small farms⁸. These modifications were primarily the result of the parceling of economically decaying landed estates⁹ and should be assessed positively.

Diametric changes in the Polish political system and relations in agriculture were introduced on the basis of the decree of the Polish Committee of National Liberation on the land reform of September 6, 1944¹⁰. Article 2 of this legal act stipulated that land owned or jointly owned by natural or legal persons would be designated for the purposes of the land reform, if the total size exceeded 100 ha of the total area, or 50 ha of agricultural land, and in the Poznań, Pomorskie and Śląskie voivodeships, if their total size exceeded 100 ha of the total area, regardless of the size of the agricultural land surface. In the light of the provisions, this agricultural real estate was immediately, without any remuneration, wholly expropriated by the State Treasury, for the purposes specified in the Act¹¹. As a rule, the transfer of land ownership under Art. 2 of the Polish Committee of National Liberation decree of September 6, 1944 took place without any remuneration. Only expropriated owners or co-owners of agricultural real estate could obtain independent farms outside the powiat (county) where the expropriated property was located. Or, if they did not exercise this right, they could be paid a monthly allowance equal to the salary of a government official of the VI group.

In the following years, state-owned agricultural enterprises (PPGR or PGR) and agricultural production cooperatives were of great importance in the country. In Poland, as probably the only socialist country, there were also private farms of farmers. It was possible thanks to patriotism and the struggle of Polish peasants. The area of land purchased by a natural person (private person), including the area of land that was already the exclusive property of the buyer or his share in joint ownership, could not exceed 15 ha, and if, due to the type of agricultural land, the agricultural property had the nature of a livestock farm, it could not exceed 20 ha. The changes were introduced after the political transformation.

⁷ E. Gorzelak, *Polityka agrarna PRL*, Warszawa 1987, pp. 45-46.

⁸ W. Grabski, *Spoleczne gospodarstwo agrarne w Polsce*. Warszawa 1923.

⁹ Ibidem.

¹⁰ Journal of Laws of 1945 No 3, item. 13 as amended, See. W. Góra, *Reforma rolna PKWN*, Warszawa 1969, p. 15 and next.

¹¹ See A. Suchoń, M. Kowalczyk, *Analiza przepisów dekretu PKWN z 6 września 1944 r. o przeprowadzeniu reformy rolnej wraz z późniejszymi zmianami oraz innych aktów prawnych na podstawie których nastąpiło przejście nieruchomości ziemskich i lasów*, [in:] *Reformy rolne w Polsce międzywojennej i powojennej*, ed. E. Borkowska-Bagieńska, W. Szafranski, Poznań 2008, pp. 63-138.

On 1 January 1992, the Agricultural Property Agency of the State Treasury started its activity¹². Its main task was to take over all state agricultural property and to manage the property in compliance with the regulations. The Agricultural Property Reserve took over the state property which used to belong to the National Land Fund or used to be a part of organized production units in the form of state agricultural companies or state agricultural farms. It is worth mentioning at this point that the National Land Fund¹³ was established on the basis of a decree of the Polish Committee of National Liberation of 6 September 1944 and it operated continuously for 48 years. Some land included in the Fund were land properties taken over by the state from former owners.

Pursuant to Article 24 of Act on 19 October 1991 on Managing Real Estate from the State Treasury and its implementing provisions¹⁴, the Agency manages the Reserve by: selling the property in full or in part; leasing or renting the property for a fixed period of time to be used, for consideration, to legal persons or natural persons; contributing the property or its part to a company; entrusting the property in full or in part to an administrator for management purposes for a fixed period of time; creating a trust; and exchanging the property. Property included in the Agricultural Property Reserve can be given, free of charge, to a local government unit under an agreement for purposes connected with the carrying out of the investment¹⁵.

By the end of December 2010, the Agricultural Property Agency had taken over properties of a surface area amounting to over 4,740,424,00 ha. For many years, lease¹⁶ was the main form of managing property. In 1995, more than 2 million 745 thousand ha were leased in Poland, in 1996 – 2 million 928 thousand ha, 1998 – 2 million 810.5 thousand ha, 2002 – 2 million 407.5 thousand ha. The sale of property, however, has recently become more popular before Poland became a member of the European Union¹⁷. Once Poland joined the European Union and fell under the Common Agricultural Policy, the need for structural changes undoubtedly increased. This results from the fact that only stable agricultural activity on bigger agricultural farms will make Polish agricultural producers competitive on the EU market and help them to use the financial aid in an effective way. This refers to such aid as that coming from the programme designed to improve agricultural farms. At the same time, it should be mentioned that some EU programs, such as structural pensions¹⁸ or bonuses for young farmers, encourage the older generation farmers to stop their agricultural activity and lead to the promotion of bigger, more modern units set up by young farmers.

¹² Under the Act of 11 April 2003 on Formation of Agricultural System the name of the Agricultural Property Agency of the State Treasury was changed to the Agricultural Property Agency. The Agricultural Property Agency is a legal successor of the Agricultural Property Agency of the State Treasury.

¹³ M. Błażejczyk M., *Prawne aspekty racjonalnego wykorzystania gruntów Państwowego Funduszu Ziemi*. Studia Prawnicze 1968, z. 18.

¹⁴ Journal of Laws of 2022 r. item 514, 1270, 1370, 1846 as amended.

¹⁵ See more P. Popardowski, Komentarz do art. 24 ustawy o gospodarowaniu nieruchomościami rolnymi Skarbu Państwa, in: Komentarz do ustawy o gospodarowaniu nieruchomościami rolnymi Skarbu Państwa, ed. K. Osajda 2021, Legalis/el.

¹⁶ A. Suchoń, *Prawna ochrona trwałości gospodarowania na dzierżawionych gruntach rolnych*, Warszawa-Poznań 2006, p. 5 and next.

¹⁷ Agricultural Property Agency, *Activity report of 2010*, <https://www.kowr.gov.pl/zasob/raporty-roczne-anr> [As on: 02.08.2022].

¹⁸ E.g. Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 30 April 2004 on the detailed conditions and procedure for granting financial aid for obtaining structural pensions covered by the rural development plan Journal of Laws

Certain restrictions in the field of agricultural real estate trading were introduced by the Act of April 11, 2003 on the shaping of the agricultural system¹⁹. The legislator then decided to use instruments of civil law: pre-emption and buyout²⁰. In the period from July 16, 2003 to April 30, 2016, this legal act did not significantly affect the structure of agricultural holdings. Major changes in the field of agricultural real estate trading were introduced by the amendment of April 14, 2016 on the shaping of the agricultural system under the Act of April 14, 2016 on suspending the sale of real estate owned by the Agricultural Property Stock of the Treasury and amending certain acts, providing for new subjective restrictions and obligations related to the acquisition of agricultural real estate. Pursuant to the Act of 11 April 2003 on Formation of Agricultural System, only an individual farmer may be the purchaser of agricultural property, unless the law provides otherwise. This legal act stipulates that the above principle does not apply to the acquisition of agricultural real estate by, for example, a relative, or a local government unit, as a result of inheritance or debt recovery²¹. Such a regulation is to limit the acquisition of agricultural land for purposes of speculation. Poland's membership in the European Union has encouraged the Polish legislator's increased interest in legal guarantees of the protection of agricultural real estate.

The subjective limitations result mainly from the fact that according to Art. 23 of the Constitution, the state's agricultural system is based on the family farm, i.e. a unit run by an individual farmer, which is a natural person who is the owner, perpetual usufructuary, sole owner, or tenant of agricultural real estate with a total area of agricultural land not exceeding 300 ha, with agricultural qualifications and at least 5 years of residence in a municipality where one of the agricultural real estates is located, and who runs the farm personally for this period. At the same time, the regulations provide for obtaining approval for the purchase of agricultural real estate issued by the National Agricultural Support Centre: at the request of the seller or the buyer, after meeting the statutory requirements. According to the novelty of Act on the Formation of the Agricultural System, since April 30, 2016 (date of the coming into force of the amendment of 14 April 2016 to the Act of 11 April 2003 on the Formation of the Agricultural System), are the obligations of the purchaser of agricultural real estate. Namely, this person is obliged to run a farm, which includes the purchased agricultural real estate, for a period of at least 10 years (and currently 5 years) from the date of purchase of this real estate, and in the case of a natural person, to run the farm in person²². During this period, the land may not be sold or given to other entities.

The Act on the Structuring the Agricultural System was amended in 2019²³, introducing the possibility of purchasing agricultural real estate up to 1 ha by persons who do not have the status of an individual farmer. This change was welcomed by those interested in small properties. Currently, the legislation in Poland is conducive to the creation and expansion of family farms. The expansion of a non-

of 2004, no 114, item 1191; Council Regulation No. 1698/2005 of 20 September 2005 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

¹⁹ Journal of Laws of 2003 No 64, item. 592 as amended. Consolidated text, Journal of Laws of 2022, item. 461, 1846.

²⁰ A. Lichorowicz, *Instrumenty oddziaływania na strukturę gruntową Polski w ustawie z dnia 11 kwietnia 2003 r. o kształtowaniu ustroju rolnego*, „Kwartalnik Prawa Prywatnego” 2004, no 1.

²¹ K. Marciniuk, *Prawne instrumenty ingerencji władzy publicznej w obrót nieruchomościami rolnymi jako środki kształtowania ustroju rolnego*, Warszawa 2019.

²² See more P. Wojciechowski, *Komentarz do art. 2b ustawy o kształtowaniu ustroju rolnego*, in : *Komentarz do ustawy o kształtowaniu ustroju rolnego*, ed. K. Osajda 2021, Legalis/el., Nb 44.

²³ Journal of Laws of 2019 item 1080.

family farm may occur, inter alia, through the lease of mainly private land and the so-called communal land. In Poland, where the vast majority of farms are run by natural persons, most have the status of family farms. There are also agricultural production cooperatives in Poland – currently over 600²⁴.

According to Article 138 of the Act of 16 September 1982 on co-operative law²⁵, the object of the agricultural activity of an agricultural production co-operative (APC) is to run a joint agricultural holding and to operate for the benefit of the individual agricultural holdings of its members. A co-operative may also engage in other business activities. The legislator used the connecting word 'and' to refer to the two basic types of activity of this type of co-operative. It seems that it is right to interpret it in a purposeful way - the APC runs a joint agricultural holding, but it may also operate for the benefit of its members' individual agricultural holdings. When defining the objectives of the APC, the legislator referred to the concept of an agricultural holding. However, the Act does not define it. Since co-operative law is classified as civil law, it is justified to refer to the definition contained in the civil code. According to the aforementioned Article 55³ of the Polish Civil Code²⁶, an agricultural holding is considered to be an agricultural land together with forest land, buildings or parts of buildings, equipment and livestock, constituting or capable of constituting an organised economic unit and rights related to running an agricultural holding. Within the set of components constituting an agricultural holding, agricultural land is given primary importance. In the case of the APC land may constitute property of that entity or be only in its possession. Special provisions of co-operative law specify the requirements to be met by members of agricultural production co-operatives. These may be farmers who are: owners or natural holders of agricultural land; tenants, users or other dependent holders of agricultural land; and may also include other persons with qualifications useful for working in a co-operative. In agricultural production co-operatives, a member has the right and obligation to work on an agricultural holding. This is provided for in Article 155 of the Act of 16 September 1982.

There are relatively few farms run by commercial companies in Poland. These are mainly entities leasing agricultural land from the National Centre for Agricultural Support, and the contracts were often concluded in the 1990s. It is worth mentioning here the legal instruments that facilitate the acquisition of agricultural real estate, the owners of which are commercial companies, by the National Agricultural Support Centre. Namely, in the event of a change of a partner or a new partner joining the partnership (general partnership, limited partnership, Kommanditgesellschaft, limited joint-stock partnership), which is the owner or perpetual usufructuary of an agricultural property with an area of at least 5 ha or agricultural property with a total area of at least 5 ha, the National Agricultural Support Center, acting for the benefit of the State Treasury, may submit a declaration on the purchase of this real estate for the payment of a price corresponding to their market value (Article 3b of the Act on Structuring the Agricultural System). In turn, according to Art. 3a of the Act on Structuring the Agricultural System, the National Agricultural Support Center, acting for the benefit of the State Treasury, has, within the meaning of the Commercial Company Code Act of 15 September 2000, the right of pre-emption of shares and stocks in a capital company, which is the owner or perpetual usufructuary of

²⁴ See more about cooperatives A. Suchoń, *Legal aspects of the organisation and operation of agricultural co-operatives in Poland*, Poznań 2019, p. 80 and next. https://press.amu.edu.pl/pub/media/produktattach/s/u/suchon_the_legal_aspects_2019__2022_oa_amup.pdf

²⁵ Uniform text: Consolidated text, Journal of Laws of 2021, item 648 as amended.

²⁶ Ustawa from 23 April 1964 - Kodeks cywilny, Polish Civil Code, Consolidated text, Journal of Laws of 2022, item. 1360 and next.

agricultural real estate with an area of at least 5 ha or agricultural real estate with a total area of at least 5 ha²⁷.

It is also worth mentioning that, on the basis of the Act of 10 February 2017 on the National Agricultural Support Centre²⁸, this institution continues the activities of the Agricultural Property Agency, the successor of the Agricultural Property Agency of the State Treasury (which began its activities in 1992). The current tasks of National Agricultural Support Centre are varied. On the one hand, it continues to manage the Treasury Property Stock, which currently amounts to over 1,346,898 ha. As of 30 June, 2022, 1,082.3 thousand ha remained under lease on the basis of 68.7 thousand lease agreements concluded²⁹. Currently, lease from the Treasury Property Stock is mainly for individual farmers and young farmers setting up farms.

On the other hand, the National Agricultural Support Centre has been obliged to implement the provisions of the Act on Structuring the Agricultural System. Therefore, the National Agricultural Support Centre influences the trade in private and communal agricultural real estate within the scope of, inter alia: examining applications and issuing administrative decisions concerning the purchase of agricultural real estate, exercising the pre-emption right and the right to acquire agricultural real estate, and supervising the fulfilment of statutory obligations by buyers of agricultural real estate. The National Support Centre for Agriculture also has broader competences, for example, in supporting measures associated with renewable energy sources, in particular in agriculture; and with monitoring the following: agricultural biogas production, the market for biocomponents and liquid biofuels, and the production of bioliquids.

According to statistical data, there were 1.3 million agricultural holdings in Poland in 2020, and when compared to 2010 their number decreased by 192,000 (by 12.7 %)³⁰. The area of agricultural holdings covered 16.4 million hectares and, compared to 2010, decreased by 587 thousand hectares (by 3.5 %). In 2020, 91.4 % of farm acreage belonged to individual farms, and this was 3.1 % more than a decade earlier. In terms of the structure of farms in 2020, every second farm belonged to the range of 1-5 ha of agricultural land (52.4 % in 2010). Farms of 5-10 ha (21.9 %, 1.0 p.p. less than in 2010) and of 15 ha and more (15.9 %, 2.9 p.p. more than in 2010) also had a large share. As in 2010, every tenth farm had an area of 10-15 ha, and the lowest share was of the smallest farms, i.e. with an area of up to 1 ha - 2.0 % (1.7 % in 2010)³¹. The average size of agricultural land in an agricultural holding in Poland in 2022 was 11.32 ha³².

3. Legal regulation and agrarian structure in Ukraine

Practically since Ukraine became part of the Soviet Union (1922), its land has belonged exclusively to the state. The forced collectivisation of the 1930s led to the creation of *kolkhozes* (collective farms)

²⁷ See more P. Blajer, W. Gonet, *Ustawa o kształtowaniu ustroju rolnego*. Komentarz, Warszawa 2020.

²⁸ Journal of Laws of 2017 item 623.

²⁹ <https://www.kowr.gov.pl/zasob> [As on: 02.08.2022].

³⁰ GUS, *Obszary wiejskie w Polsce w 2020 r.*

³¹ GUS, *Obszary wiejskie w Polsce w 2020 r.*, p. 101 and next.

³² Announcement of the President of the Agency for Restructuration and Modernization of Agriculture of September 15, 2022 on the size of the average area of agricultural land in a farm in individual provinces and the average area of agricultural land in a farm in the country in 2021, <https://www.gov.pl/web/arimr/srednia-powierzchnia-gruntow-rolnych-w-gospodarstwie-w-2022-roku> [As on: 02.08.2022].

and *sovkhozes* (state enterprises) reaped the benefits of using the land free of charge. Only in 1991, after Ukraine gained independence, land reform began with the former collective farms, which were transformed into collective agricultural enterprises (*KSP*), in accordance with the Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine “On Land Reform” of December 18, 1990 (this resolution is not currently in force), Laws of Ukraine “On Forms of Ownership on Land” of January 30, 1992³³, (no longer in force) and the Law “About the collective agricultural farm” of November 14, 1992³⁴.

These laws recognised the right granted to each of the employees the right to a proportionate share of the *kolkhoz* land (a so-called “pai”). The process of determining the size of the pai (1–8 ha, depending on the district) lasted about ten years and, according to various data, 6–8 million people received certificates confirming their right to them. During the initial stage of the agrarian reform, 10,800 former collective farms (*kolkhozes*) were reorganised into collective agricultural farms (*KSP*). More than 2,300 state farms (practically the same as PGR in Poland) and other state-owned enterprises were also privatized.

Although during this time the entire *kolkhoz* land was “allocated”, only the area of land which fell to a given person was determined, without marking out plots on maps, let alone in the field (this was to be done only if the owner of the *pai* wanted to leave the *kolkhoz* and farm independently). The vast majority of land ownership certificates were leased to the heads of agri-companies, and only about 6 % of them were converted into the right to use a specific, physically separate plot of land.

In the same period, namely in 1992, the first Land Code of independent Ukraine was adopted. According to this legislation, the land fund of the country ceased to be the exclusive property of the state, and land plots could be in state, collective, and private ownership. Article 4 of the Code listed land that could not be transferred to collective or private ownership, and all other land could be privatised. The 1992 Land Code did not allow private ownership of land plots by legal entities. Legal entities could receive land plots for permanent or short-term use, as well as for lease for a period not exceeding 50 years.

The next stage of land reform was the definition of land shares (agricultural land). As of June 1 2001 6,480,000 peasants became owners of certificates confirming their right to a land parcel (share or *pai*). During these years, there was an active privatization process when there was no prohibition on the sale of land shares (*paji*). The issued decrees determined the procedure for the circulation of arable land. All agreements had to be notarized and registered, which the state was not ready for. So 65.5 % (or 27.4 million ha) of arable land had been privatized by the end of 1997. The most successful measures have been the privatization of small plots of land, mainly with houses on them, which can be bought and sold.

The main phases of this period are: 1995 – the Presidential Decree “On the Procedure for the Sharing of Land Transferred Into Collective Ownership of Agricultural Enterprises and Organizations”; 2001 – the Adoption of the Law “On Agreements on the Alienation of a Land Portion”. In 2001, the new Land Code of Ukraine was enacted, establishing ownership of agricultural land. But it was believed that the country was not prepared for the introduction of free trade in land (in part due to the lack of a land

³³ The Law of Ukraine No. 2073-XII “On Forms of Ownership on Land” of January 30, 1992, no longer in force.

³⁴ The Law of Ukraine No.2114-XII “About the collective agricultural farm” of November 14, 1992.

cadastre) and therefore the implementation of the legislation was suspended until the necessary conditions were met³⁵.

The first interim act prohibiting the purchase of land and establishing the first moratorium was passed in 2001. This regulation was established for three years to regulate the market during this time. However, the “temporary moratorium” was prolonged eight times. The sale of land was mothballed, and only 2 areas were developed: gratuitous privatization of land (the possibility of each individual receiving 2 ha of land from the community and land lease).

It must be mentioned that during this time, there has been a concentration of land and the creation of large agricultural enterprises (called agri-holdings in Ukraine), farming on tens or – in some cases – hundreds of thousands of hectares leased from the owners of *pais*. At the same time, the former *kolkhoz* workers, some of whom had no heirs, were dying out. The area of such no-man's-land is steadily increasing, and is currently estimated at 1.6 million ha. The possibility of the free use of this land motivated both entrepreneurs and officials, who corruptly profited from this procedure, the reform of the ownership situation in agriculture.

This period began in 2011, when the Law “On State Land Cadastre” was adopted. It took the Ukrainian parliament 30 years to pass the Law on the Land Market. It was only during Zelensky's presidency that the long-awaited Law of Ukraine from the 31 March 2020 No. 552-IX “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Circulation of Agricultural Land”, the basis for the entire land reform, was adopted³⁶.

However, the implementation of the this law will be gradual:

- From July 1, 2021 only individuals – citizens of Ukraine may purchase agricultural land. And they may not buy more than 100 hectares per person.
- From January 1, 2024, legal entities registered in Ukraine and founded by a citizen of Ukraine will be able to purchase more than 10 thousand hectares.

The land market has opened, but the purchase and sale of land are proceeding rather slowly because of the unprepared infrastructure: the complexity of the legal processing of agreements, the incompleteness and absence of land in electronic registers. But now foreigners and foreign companies are not allowed to acquire ownership of agricultural lands in Ukraine until the applause (sub-question) of this question at the all-Ukrainian referendum. At this time, the mechanism of the all-Ukrainian referendum has not been clearly defined: it is not known when it will take place and under what conditions.

As a result of the aforementioned reform, the ownership structure of agricultural land in Ukraine (41,4 million ha) is now as follows³⁷: 1) private ownership – 31 million ha (74.9 %); 2) state ownership – 8.7 million ha (21 %); 3) communal ownership – 1.7 million ha (4.1 %). In 2020 the structure of agricultural land use was as follows: 1) land that is cultivated by its owners – 29 %; 2) land leased from owners – 56 %; 3) land leased from the state – 8 %; 4) land that is not cultivated – 7 %. Overall, Ukraine has formed a large group of landowners and land users – 25.3 million people and 6,9 million owners

³⁵ P.F. Kulynych, *Zemelna reforma v Ukraini: pravovi problem*. Monografia. Kyiv: Norma prava, 2021. 308.

³⁶ The Law of Ukraine No. 552-IX “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Circulation of Agricultural Land” of March 13, 2020.

³⁷ *Zemelny dovidnyk Ukrainy 2020*. – <https://kurkul.com/spetsproekty/1094-zemlya-dlya-fermera-dovidniki-zakoni-i-poradi-yuristiv-ta-ekspertiv> [As on: 02.08.2022].

of land shares. In the year 2000, a total of 14,700 new companies were established on the basis of 11,400 KSPs. Among them: 1,254 peasant farms, 6,761 business partnerships (mostly of them were in form of LLC), 2,901 private and rented enterprises, 3,325 agricultural cooperatives and over 500 other business entities.

The number and role of different enterprises has changed over the years, but their overall structure has remained the same³⁸. Therefore, four main groups of agricultural producers can now be distinguished in Ukrainian agriculture: 1) households – also including persons–entrepreneurs, who are not legal entities and who grow agricultural products both for their own needs and for sale; 2) private enterprises – in agriculture they are represented by farms and private agriculture enterprises. Farms may be established exclusively by citizens of Ukraine and their activities must be based on the labour of the members of the farmer's family, although the hiring of workers is permitted. The land may be owned by the farmer as the right of ownership. The size of farms can also vary from a few hectares to 5000-10,000 hectares, which is effectively a medium-sized enterprise. More than 60 % of the farms have an area of 100 to 2,000 hectares. Private agricultural enterprises are legal entities that operate on the basis of private property and may be founded by citizens of Ukraine, as well as foreigners, stateless persons and legal entities. The general rules of the Civil Code and the Commercial Code on the conduct of business activities apply to them;

3) collectively owned enterprises, different forms of cooperatives. Cooperatives in Ukraine can be of different types. The most common are production cooperatives and service cooperatives. A *producer cooperative is established exclusively by individuals for joint production or other economic activities on the basis of their obligatory participation in labour for the purpose of making a profit*. A service cooperative is established by natural and/or legal persons to provide services primarily to the members of the cooperative, but also to other persons for the purpose of carrying out their business activities. Among other things, the development of cooperatives was to be encouraged by the new Law “On agricultural cooperatives” of July 21, 2020³⁹, which made significant changes to the rules of cooperatives and changed their classification. In addition to this, all types of agricultural cooperatives operating by 15.11.2020 must be re-registered within 3 years, i.e. by 15.11.2023.

4) business partnerships – can be either domestic, foreign or with foreign investment. In the agricultural sector, business partnerships are the most common form of business after farms. They are predominantly in the form of limited liability and joint-stock partnerships.

Ukraine stands out for the high percentage of land cultivated by agricultural companies (agri-companies). In 2019, individual farmers utilised only 27 % of the land. The share of companies in production varies depending on the crop type – it is the highest in the case of oilseeds (rapeseed, sunflower and soybean), cereals (maize, wheat and barley) and sugar beets.

Agri-companies are very fragmented, with the vast majority leasing land of less than 100 ha. The largest players (above 3,000 ha) constitute about 1 % of all companies operating in the agri-food sector and produce more than 20 % of cereals and oilseeds. The most important position, however, is held by medium-sized companies with an acreage of 200–2000 ha. There are about 6,000 of them and,

³⁸ UKAB. Vydy silskohospodarskyh pidpryjemstv v Ukraini. – <https://kurkul.com/spetsproekty/1094-zemlya-dlya-fermera-dovidniki-zakoni-i-poradi-yuristiv-ta-ekspertiv> [As on: 05.08.2022].

³⁹ The Law of Ukraine No. 819-IX "On agricultural cooperatives" of July 21, 2020.

depending on the species cultivated, they are responsible for cultivating 50–75 % of the land tilled by the companies.

The subsequent development of the agricultural sector, based on a system of land renting, has led to the emergence of a new type of companies, called agri-holding. This process was greatly accelerated with the adoption of the Land Code in 2001. Ukrainian agri-holdings are distinguished by their having a large share of foreign capital (the largest portion comes from the USA and Saudi Arabia); entities from outside the country own around 10 % of agricultural land. This is a significant difference in comparison to other sectors of the economy, where, apart from electricity distribution and a metallurgy, the whole industry remains under the control of a few local oligarchs. The largest agricultural producers have a holding structure and list their shares on world stock exchanges. In Warsaw, a separate index was even created targeting mainly local agri-companies (WIG Ukraine).

In 2019, there were twenty-two entities in Ukraine leasing an area of more than 50,000 ha, ten of which were in charge of more than 100,000 ha. In total, they cultivated about 3.4 million ha of land (12 % of all agricultural land). A very interesting fact is that the term “agri-holding” does not exist in Ukrainian law. It is commonly used to describe the largest companies operating in the agri-food market, which adopt a holding structure to optimise their management. Ukrainian agri-holdings can be divided into those owned by agri-oligarchs and foreign investors. Compared to other sectors of the economy, agriculture is distinguished by having a fairly large share of foreign capital. This applies to both large agri-holdings (the American-owned *Agroprosperis* or *Continental Farmers Group*, owned by the Saudi fund SALIC) and small and medium-sized enterprises.

4. Conclusion

Although Poland and Ukraine are two neighboring and friendly countries, today there is a substantial difference in their agrarian structure. Before the Second World War, both in Poland and in parts of Ukraine there were farms of medium size, the so-called gentry farms, and small peasant farms. The agrarian reforms of 1920, 1925 in Poland (on the basis of which the state bought part of the agricultural land from the owners of large estates and sold it to small farms to enlarge their area) were aimed at modernizing the agrarian structure.

In 1930th collective farms were established in the Ukrainian territories that were then part of the Soviet Union. After the Second World War, land reform was carried out in Poland and Ukraine. In Poland, from 1945 to 1989, in addition to state farms and agricultural production cooperatives, small individual farms, generally up to 15 ha, persisted. They could be established and operated throughout the socialist period. However, in Ukraine agricultural land belonged to the state. After the transformation of the political system in Poland in 1989-1991 and Ukraine’s declaration of independence in 1991, further changes took place. In Poland, long-established individual farms developed and many entities increased their acreage by purchasing or leasing land from the Agricultural Property Stock of the State Treasury. At the same time, new farms were established, including commercial companies run by people such as those managing state-owned farms.

In Ukraine by carrying out the reform and transferring agricultural real estate with an area of 8 ha to the employees of collective farms (which was often quite formal), it seems that legislator appreciated the long-term work of the employees of these units in those country. In practice, however, it

turned out that these persons were not prepared to carry out agricultural activities themselves in Ukraine. Consequently, a great number of lease agreements were concluded with agri-holdings, whose shareholders are often foreign companies. Some of the companies acquired real estate on their own.

The current agrarian structure of Poland and Ukraine is therefore different. The former is dominated by farms run by individuals, generally having the status of a family farm. There are few agricultural holding companies and about 600 agricultural cooperatives. Family farms are the basis of the agricultural system and the legislator has supported and will continue to support such entities in the future. The average farm in Poland is about 12 ha. In Ukraine, on the other hand, more than 60 % of agricultural land with an area of between 200 and 2,000 ha is leased. Agri-holdings are of great importance. In view of its status as a candidate for membership of the European Union, Ukraine should carry out a reform to strengthen the position of Ukrainian farmers. In the European Union, family farms are the most popular in the majority of countries. It must of course be acknowledged, however, that Ukraine currently has other problems to contend with. Russia's invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022 has already caused enormous damage to the Ukrainian agrarian economy. Of course, it is still difficult to assess the extent of the damage accurately at this stage. Just the indirect losses in agriculture due to production decrease, logistics disruption and lower prices for export-oriented commodities were estimated at USD 23.3 billion (at the middle of June). This is stated in the analysis "Agricultural War Losses Review Ukraine. Rapid Loss Assessment", prepared by the team of the Center for Food Research and Land Use at KSE (*Kyiv School of Economics*) Institute (KSE Agrocenter) in cooperation with the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine⁴⁰.

⁴⁰ Kyiv School of Economics (KSE). Ohliad zbytkiv ta vtrat v APK. – <https://kse.ua/ua/oglyad-zbitkiv-ta-vtrat-v-apk/>[As on: 05.08.2022].